

Magnetic recording in rocks and sediments.

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Abstract : *Rock magnetic measurements are relatively fast, non-destructive, cheap and can be performed on bulk samples. They have been extensively used in palaeoclimatic and environmental pollution monitoring studies for the last two decades. There are several ways that magnetic particles occur in rocks. In igneous rocks the magnetic minerals are crystallized from lavas. In sediments the magnetic material stems from several sources. The increase of industries, especially during the last four decades has produced considerable amount of environmental pollution. Especially the iron bearing processes are mainly responsible for input of magnetic particles into the environment. Especially magnetite containing spherules are the most common constituents in fly ash and bottom ash, which result from combustion of coal and oil. the origin of magnetic minerals will be presented in this paper as well as parameters which are used to deduce the magnetic grain size, mineral composition and concentration.*

Introduction

Magnetic properties can be used as a proxy for several environmental processes as they are quite sensitive to grain size variations, concentration and composition (Verosub and Roberts, 1995; Thompson and Oldfield, 1986). Rock magnetic measurements are relatively fast, non-destructive, cheap and can be performed on bulk samples. They have been extensively used in palaeoclimatic and environmental pollution monitoring studies for the last two decades. The basic principles of palaeomagnetism and the origin of magnetic minerals will be presented in this paper as well as parameters which are used to deduce the magnetic grain size, mineral composition and concentration.

Natural remanent magnetization (NRM)

Iron oxides are abundant in almost all rocks. These magnetic minerals can carry a permanent magnetic moment,

which is termed as natural remanent magnetization (NRM). Primary remanent magnetization is acquired during the rock formation, which depends on the local geomagnetic field and geological processes. Over geological time the rock may acquire new remanence components, which are added to the existing NRM, referred as secondary remanent component. The secondary remanence alters the primary NRM partially or completely. The sum of primary and secondary components gives the total NRM. The primary remanence plays the central role for palaeomagnetic investigations. The main types of remanent magnetization are 1) thermoremanent magnetization, acquired during cooling from above the Curie temperature in the presence of a magnetic field 2) chemical remanent magnetization, formed by alteration or new formation of ferro(i)magnetic grains below their Curie temperatures and 3) detrital remanent

magnetization, acquired during accumulation of sedimentary rocks containing detrital ferro(i)magnetic particles. The primary component can be resolved from total NRM by stepwise demagnetizing of the sample using either increasing alternating field (AF demagnetization) or increasing temperatures (thermal demagnetization) in a magnetic field free space. The distribution of magnetic grains in a sample should be ideally isotropic and the primary magnetization must have long relaxation times in order to record a faithful directional record. Changes in magnetic field with time tend the magnetic grains to align in the new field. The tendency of the magnetic grains aligning to new magnetic field depends on the height of energy barrier. When the process of new alignment occurs in short period they are said to have short relaxation (order of seconds to days) and when the alignment process occurs slowly or is negligible with respect to geological time scale, the relaxation time is said to be long (could be in the order of age of the Earth). After removal of the magnetizing field the magnetic remanence M_r decrease exponentially with time i.e. $M_r(t) = M_r(t_0)e^{-t/\tau}$ where τ is the characteristic relaxation time after which $M_r = M_r(t_0)/e$. Louis Néel showed that for SD grains the characteristic relaxation time is given by equation

$$\tau = \frac{1}{C} \exp\left(\frac{\mu_0 v h_c M_s}{2kT}\right)$$

Where C is the frequency factor $\sim 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (means how quickly the atomic spins can reorient within magnetic material). μ_0, v, h_c, M_s are free-space permeability, volume, microscopic coercivity and saturation magnetization, k is Boltzmann constant and T is absolute temperature. $\mu_0 v h_c M_s$ is referred to the energy barrier and kT is the thermal

energy. Relaxation times and magnetic properties steadily change as a function of domain structures. There are four basic types of structures (domain states). The smallest grains with shortest relaxation times ($\tau < \sim 150 \text{ s}$) are superparamagnetic grains. Slightly bigger grains are called single domain (SD). The SD range for magnetite is ~ 0.03 to $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ for spherical shape and can be bigger for elongated particles. Still larger grains, which contain few domains are called pseudo-single domain (PSD). They are called so because their magnetic properties resemble SD grains. For magnetite the upper threshold of PSD grains is $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$. The largest grains ($> \sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ for magnetite) are said to be multidomain (MD). The domain state of grains mainly depend on the size of the magnetic particle and its composition. SD grains have extremely high relaxation times (in order of the age of the Earth). The relaxation time decreases with increase of grain size from PSD to MD grain sizes. The SP grains have the lowest relaxation times. The above-mentioned equation is valid for SP and SD grains.

Sources of magnetic minerals

Natural occurrence

There are several ways that magnetic particles occur in rocks. In igneous rocks the magnetic minerals are crystallized from lavas. In sediments the magnetic material stems from several sources. Metamorphic rocks contain initial and newly formed magnetic minerals.

Detrital particles are physically and/or chemically eroded and transported to the depositional site. Some diagenetic process take place during or shortly after deposition. Bacteria and intercellular magnetosomes that use iron in their metabolism and poor crystalline magnetite are known to occur outside of

the cell referred as extracellular magnetite (Biogenic particles). Authigenic particles, which are formed in-situ due to chemical processes. Iron sulfides are known to be the most commonly occurring in this process.

Anthropogenic occurrence

The increase of industries especially during the last four decades has produced considerable amount of environmental pollution. Especially the iron bearing processes are mainly responsible for input of magnetic particles into environment. Especially magnetite containing spherules are the most common constituents in fly ash and bottom ash, which result from combustion of coal and oil. Road and rail transport also play a role in input of magnetic particles (mainly by abrasion) into the environment. The magnetic properties of anthropogenic origin differ from the ones of natural origin (Oldfield et al., 1985) Dunlop, D.J. and Özdemir, O., 1997.

Estimation of concentration and grain-size

The different process and origins of magnetic particles has an influence on the magnetic concentration, particle-size distribution and mineralogy of the magnetic component. The rock magnetic parameters (such as susceptibility (χ), anhysteretic remanent magnetization (ARM), saturation isothermal remanent magnetization (SIRM), isothermal remanent magnetization (IRM), saturation magnetization (M_s)) and their ratios can be used to characterize the magnetic components of sediments and soils.

Rock magnetic parameters, χ , ARM, SIRM and M_s indicate mainly magnetic concentration. They increase with increasing magnetic concentration and are also dependent on magnetic mineralogy. ARM and SIRM are grain size

dependent and they show an increase in presence of higher proportion of fine grain (single domain) magnetic particles. χ is also dependent on grain sizes; it is dominant in presence of larger and very fine grain sizes (multi-domain and superparamagnetic). M_s is independent of grain sizes and show maximum values for magnetite and maghemite. SIRM shows relatively low values in presence of lower magnetization minerals (e.g. hematite). Especially in sediments, the remanence bearing minerals occur in low proportions and the para and diamagnetic components can extensively control χ . In this case the laboratory induced remanences ARM and SIRM would be extensively useful to determine concentration of ferro(i)magnetic phases.

The interparameter ratios ARM/ χ and ARM/SIRM signify primarily the grain size variations and are also dependent on magnetic mineral content. These ratios vary inversely with magnetic grain size. Both ratios primarily reflect the presence of finer grain sizes (single domain) and also can be used to detect the relative changes in concentration of finer magnetic grain sizes. The S-ratio ($-IRM/SIRM$) and HIRM ($(-IRM+SIRM)/2$) indicate the concentration of hard magnetic phase. Values of S ratio close to 1 indicate softer magnetic components and lower values indicate higher concentrations of harder components like hematite and goethite. Values of HIRM are proportional to the content of high coercivity minerals (hematite and goethite).

Non-magnetic techniques for analyzing magnetic phases

Mineral magnetic changes depend on different climatic processes. Identifying magnetic mineralogy is of primary importance for any palaeoclimatic interpretation. Apart from

the identification of mineralogy through magnetic techniques, it is always necessary to substantiate them using independent analysis. To examine the magnetic minerals, they need to be extracted from the bulk samples and analyzed by standard methods like Mößbauer spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). However, these analyses are strongly influenced by strongly magnetic minerals as they are more inclined to be separated during extraction from the soils or sediment matrix.

The rock magnetic parameters are ambiguous and do not represent a palaeoclimatic proxy per se. The magnetic variations are to be verified with other direct palaeoclimatic proxies like pollen, carbonate, Total organic carbon (TOC), etc. Once they are verified for a certain case (e.g. a lake) they can be used as a tool for high resolution studies of palaeoclimatic changes.

Magnetic stratigraphy

Magnetic stratigraphy was initially used to organize young igneous rock strata based on stratigraphic intervals and similar magnetic characteristics. It was consecutively developed and was extended to older geomagnetic polarity time scales using sedimentary environments. The magnetic characteristic most often used is the polarity of magnetic remanence. The pattern of polarity zones is determined by measuring the magnetic remanence vectors of samples taken from the stratigraphic section. The polarity is said to be normal when the north seeking magnetization gives the northern hemisphere pole (as today) and reverse when the north seeking magnetization gives the southern hemisphere pole. The

systematic change in geomagnetic polarity along long sequences has set a fundamental application of dating. Studies have shown that the oceanic crustal record only goes back to the late Callovian (latest Middle Jurassic) anywhere on Earth (Ogg, 1995), whereas the older polarity time scales are confined to volcanic and sedimentary sequences on land. The magnetostratigraphic studies on land have proven that they are accurate and resolved some of the short polarity events, which were not clear in marine sequences (Lowrie et al., 1980b). Studies of Cande and Kent (1995) have given a more detailed polarity timescale of the last 120 million years which intensified the precision of geomagnetic polarity dating.

In sediments the primary remanence is acquired by alignment of ferro(i)magnetic particles in the ambient magnetic field during or shortly after the deposition, termed as depositional or post depositional remanence magnetization (pDRM). The recording is efficient in calm environment depositional systems particularly in fine-grained homogenous sediments. However the exact mechanism of remanence acquisition process is still not completely understood (Kent, 1973, Verosub, 1977). Resolving the primary remanence (remanence acquired during deposition) along the stratigraphy is the fundamental requirement of magnetostratigraphy. Enormous amount of magnetostratigraphy work was done on Quaternary deposits and their dates were well established around the globe.

Lacustrine sediments are a suitable archive for records of palaeoenvironmental changes on different time scales (e.g. Thouveny et al., 1994; Williams et al., 1997; Wang et al., 1999). A reliable and accurate age frame is a fundamental requirement for any such interpretation. Radiocarbon dating

provides a powerful tool for periods younger than about 60 ka. Beyond the range of ^{14}C lifetime absolute dating methods are very limited. Magnetostratigraphy has been particularly successful for long sequences (e.g. Kashmir basin; Burbank and Johnson, 1982).

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